

EXPRESSION OF THE CONCEPTS OF "BEAUTY/UGLINESS" IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND PAREMIOLOGY

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It is known that the phraseological fund of the language is an important source of information reflecting the customs, lifestyle, culture and mentality of a certain people. Because the myths, customs, traditions, and customs of a certain nation are reflected in phraseology. Phraseologisms play a special role in creating a linguistic picture of the world or seeing the world through the means of language. Phraseological units are important tools that create imagery, expressiveness and emotionality, and they play an important role in increasing the expressive effectiveness of artistic texts. That is why phraseological units (FUs) are compact, meaningful and impressive units. Phraseological units are inextricably linked with the spirituality, customs, profession, lifestyle, past, and attitude of the people who own the language. V.V. Taking into account the motivation of FUs, Vinogradov divides them into three types: phraseological combination, phraseological combination and phraseological units (5;7).

Analyzing phraseological units, N. Amosova divides FUs into two groups depending on whether one or all of their components are figurative: if one of the components in FUs is figurative; puts forward the idea of calling them "phrase" and "idiom" if all the components are figurative (6; 123).

A.I. Smirnitsky makes FUs equivalent to words and emphasizes that they occur as part of a sentence in a sentence (7;254).

In world linguistics, until now, the field of phraseology is understood in a broad and narrow sense. Scholars who understand phraseology in a wide range include proverbs, sayings, aphorisms and other types of stable units (3;344).

Uzbek linguist Sh. Rakhmatullaev proposes to call the units characteristic of the phraseological layer "phraseme" (4; 405).

In most genres of folklore, the image of animals, plants, and birds is used in phraseological units in order to express various relations, events and situations in society more simply and clearly. Taking each of these as a symbol, the image of people with certain positive and negative qualities is reinforced and embodied through them. Below we will focus on the analysis of phraseological units expressing "beauty/ugliness" in English and Uzbek languages.

From the results of the analysis of the phraseological dictionaries of the English language, we have seen that there are much phraseology expressing the

appearance of a person. It should also be noted that the phraseological material in the English language is more focused on expressing beautiful appearance than on expressing ugliness. We can see the expression of the beautiful appearance of a person in the following phrases: *sweets to the sweet; out of this world; graceful as a swan; prince charming; as pretty as a picture; may queen; soft as down; as handsome as a painting; as shining as star;*

Paremiological units are proverbs and sayings - folk judgments, which confirm or deny something clearly, expressively, effectively, that is, they express the truth. Each nation has its own system of proverbs and sayings, which reflect the customs, mentality and traditions of the nation. Proverbs and sayings, when used in communication, have a strong impact on the interlocutor and serve to quickly understand the topic. The results of the analysis revealed that in both languages, proverbs are used to describe the beauty of women more than men.

It is also worth noting that proverbs focus more on the pleasantness and beauty of a person's appearance, height and behavior. For example, 1. Proverbs expressing the beauty of a person's appearance: *A pretty man looks pretty in every clothing; If you are beautiful, whatever you do is fine; Good face is a letter of recommendation; Every woman would rather be handsome than good; Like Beauty is a living thing.* 2. Pleasant, expressing the possession of good behavior: *Good fame is better than a good face; A clear conscience shines not only a good face; Faults are thick where love is thin; Beauty is silent eloquence; Fair words break no bones; Like a bird is known by its note and a man by his talk.*

3. Proverbs expressing that beauty and love go hand in hand with lies: *Beauty lies in lover's eyes; Beauty is in the eye of the beholder; He who loves at one-eyed girl thinks that one-eyed girls are beautiful; Beautiful roads never go far; Like what blossoms beautifully, withers fast.*

Beauty is expressed as a result of subjective assessment in English by the following proverb: *Every mother thinks her own gosling a swan.* The same situation in Uzbek language: *Ҳамманики ўзига, ой кўринар кўзига; Қўнғиз ҳам боласини оппоғим, тунпратикан юшоғим дейди.*

Proverbs about the disproportion of beauty leads to ugliness. *Дидсиз ўтирган ерини ҳам чангитар; Йиртиқ тўнга – зар ямоқ; Кал бошига – шамшод тароқ; Сўқир кўзга сурманинг кераги йўқ; Ўрдак ўзига оро берса ҳам, оққуш бўлолмас.*

From the results of the research, it became clear that lexemes representing beauty can be further divided into the following groups and analyzed:

1) Do not judge based on appearance alone: *Beauty is but/only skin-deep; Appearances are deceptive/deceitful.* In Uzbek: *Чиройли хотин кўча кўрки, ақлли хотин уй кўрки; Чиройига нон ботириб еб бўлмас.*

1) 2) About being more beautiful on the inside than on the outside: *Virtue lives when beauty dies; A fair face may hide a foul heart/soul; Fair without, foul (false) within.* In Uzbek: *Чирой тўйда керак, ақл кунда керак; Усти ялтироқ, ичи қалтироқ;*

3) Regarding the fact that everyone has a different idea of beauty: *Tastes differ; Beauty is in the eye of the gazer/beholder; Beauty is in the beholder's eye.* In Uzbek: *Ҳар кимни диди ҳар хил;*

4) Clothing is a decoration of a person: *Fine feathers make fine birds; The tailor makes the man.* In Uzbek: *Clothing is a person's decoration; Кийимига қараб қутиб олинади, ақлига қараб қузатишади.*

We have seen that in English people's culture, when expressing ugliness, more attention is paid to its unpleasant appearance and behavior. For example, expressing the unpleasantness and ugliness of human appearance or body parts: Never look up to others thinking you are ugly, instead be so successful that they look up to you; When you humiliate an ugly person do remember that it is the ugliness of your eyes; You are what you think about yourself, if you think yourself as ugly you will never overcome this thought.

Ugly behavior: Pretty people give their lives trying to look better; ugly people give their life to make their lives better; True love is found in the character and personality and not whether they are beautiful or ugly; Laughing at ugly ones will get you nothing; remember that your beauty will fade over time; Nothing is more ugly than your hatred towards someone; Devil is the ugliest of all creations, sometimes they appear in the form of angels; An honest and trustworthy man becomes ugly when he is driven by greed for money; "Your ugliness depends on how you perceive things, not what others say; "The ugliness of the face does not matter, but the ugliness of the heart does.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the phraseology of the English language, more importance is attached to the appearance and clothing of the primary person. In the culture of the Uzbek people, situations related to human inner beauty, behavior, and mental processes are reflected. Also, in the paremiological unit system of the compared languages, we can observe to a certain extent linguistic and cultural similarities and differences. In this case, it was found that analytical tools prevail in English, while agglutinative tools prevail in Uzbek.

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